

MEDICAL SCIENCES

TREATMENT AND PREVENTION OF GUM BLEEDING

Demirchiyeva Mehriban Vidadi

*Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Assistant
Department of Therapeutic c Dentistry*

Huseynova Rena Nadir

Department of Therapeutic c Dentistry Assistant

Gurskaya Narmina Azad

*Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine Assistant
Department of Orthopedics Dentistry*

*Azerbaijan Medical University,
Baku, Azerbaijan*

Abstract

Gum bleeding is a common symptom that can indicate various oral diseases and may also result from systemic disorders of the body. This issue is particularly relevant in dental practice, as timely identification of the cause of gum bleeding not only helps eliminate the local pathological process but also prevents the development of more serious diseases.

Keywords: gum bleeding, causes, prevention

Physiological Basis of Gum Bleeding: The gums are made up of dense connective tissue covered by mucous membrane. They provide protection for the tooth-gum junction against external influences and microbes. One of the key functions of the gums is to act as a barrier between the tooth and the surrounding tissues, preventing the penetration of pathogenic microorganisms. Bleeding occurs when the integrity of the blood vessels in the gum papilla or mucous membrane is disrupted. The causes of this phenomenon can be local (related to the oral cavity) or systemic (associated with general health conditions).

Main Causes of Gum Bleeding:

- **Gingivitis:** This is inflammation of the gum tissue caused by the accumulation of dental plaque and tartar, where bacteria actively multiply. The main symptoms include redness, swelling, and gum bleeding when brushing teeth.

- **Periodontitis:** A more severe disease, periodontitis involves the destruction of the tissues surrounding the tooth, potentially leading to tooth loss. Bleeding can occur even at rest. Using a hard toothbrush or improper brushing techniques can traumatize the gum mucosa. Insufficient or irregular tooth brushing leads to the accumulation of plaque, which is the primary cause of inflammatory processes in the gums.

A lack of vitamins, especially vitamin C (ascorbic acid), weakens the blood vessel walls and increases the tendency to bleed. Vitamin K, involved in blood clotting, is also essential for preventing gum bleeding.

Hormonal Changes: During pregnancy or puberty, hormonal fluctuations can cause gum bleeding. These changes increase the sensitivity of gum tissues to inflammation.

In diabetic patients, microcirculation in the tissues is impaired, increasing the risk of inflammatory processes, including gum bleeding.

Systemic blood clotting disorders, such as hemophilia, can manifest as gum bleeding due to impaired clotting ability.

Weakened immunity increases the risk of infections in the oral cavity, leading to gum bleeding.

Certain medications, such as anticoagulants, can cause side effects that result in increased bleeding tendencies, including gum bleeding.

Diagnosis of the Causes of Gum Bleeding

To accurately determine the cause of gum bleeding, a dentist must conduct a thorough examination and gather the patient's medical history. The diagnostic process includes:

1. Oral Examination:

Visual assessment of the condition of the gums, presence of dental plaque, tartar, and mucosal damage.

2. Visual Evaluation:

Checking for the appearance of gum inflammation, plaque accumulation, tartar, and any damage to the mucous membrane of the gums.

3. Instrumental Methods:

Bleeding on Probing Index (BOP): This index quantitatively measures the degree of inflammation by checking for bleeding when probing the gums.

Radiography: X-rays may help detect bone tissue destruction, which is important for diagnosing periodontitis.

4. Laboratory Tests:

Complete Blood Count (CBC): To rule out systemic diseases that could contribute to gum bleeding.

Glucose Level Determination: This test is crucial if there is suspicion of diabetes, as high glucose levels can affect gum health.

Coagulation Profile (Coagulogram): To diagnose blood clotting disorders that may cause excessive gum bleeding.

Treatment Methods for Gum Bleeding

The treatment for gum bleeding depends on its underlying cause and may include the following interventions:

Choosing a soft-bristled toothbrush and antibacterial toothpaste.

Using dental floss or an irrigator to remove plaque from interdental spaces.

Removal of dental plaque and tartar using ultrasonic devices or manual tools to address the main cause of inflammation.

Antiseptic solutions (e.g., chlorhexidine) for mouth rinses to reduce bacteria in the oral cavity.

Anti-inflammatory ointments and gels containing metronidazole or chlorhexidine.

Vitamin therapy (vitamins C, K, and B complex).

If gum bleeding is caused by underlying systemic conditions, specialists such as endocrinologists, hematologists, or therapists may be needed for diagnosis and treatment.

Increasing the intake of vitamin-rich foods, such as citrus fruits, leafy vegetables, and dairy products, can support gum health.

To prevent gum bleeding, the following recommendations should be followed:

1. Visit the dentist regularly (at least twice a year).
2. Brush teeth twice a day for two minutes using proper technique.
3. Have professional oral hygiene procedures done 1–2 times a year.
4. Maintain a balanced diet and take vitamins as prescribed by a doctor.

5. Control chronic conditions and avoid self-medication.

Conclusion

Gum bleeding is not just a local issue but could be a sign of more serious health conditions. Accurate diagnosis and timely treatment can help not only eliminate the symptom but also prevent complications. The key role in this process belongs to the dentist, who should educate patients about the importance of prevention and regular oral care.

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